

Attention Anomalies as Measured By Time Estimation Under G Stress

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To investigate attention anomalies under G stress, performance tests involving the estimation of time duration were conducted at sustained levels of 1 Gz, 3 Gz, and 5 Gz stress for a duration of 60 seconds. Two types of time estimation tasks were conducted—counting and noncounting. Analysis of these data across all subjects indicates that the estimation of the minimum duration counting task was grossly underestimated. Data were first analyzed across all subjects and only the shortest counting task was affected by the 5 Gz stress condition. Overall, however, for a given stress level, the counting task was much more accurate a method to estimate time as compared to noncounting. The 5 Gz stress level was slightly below the threshold to effect performance, however, for the documented case of one subject under great mental stress, his results were significantly affected by the combination of 5 Gz stress and the psychological stress. This effort has identified the 5 Gz stressor as the level where performance begins to degrade, subject to the level of mental stress experienced by the subject.

Introduction: In the military scenario, involving high G stress, which occurs in today's modern fighter aircraft such as F-16s or in training aircraft such as T-37s and T-38s, pilot error, and consequently a possible cause of aircraft mishaps, may be due to a form of attention anomaly induced by the G stress (1,2,3). One possible metric to evaluate attention anomalies that occur would be the human's perception of the passage of time. Heuristically, one would expect that passage of time would be biased under G stress. If this were the case, then a pilot's performance deteriorates in a subtle way that would be difficult to test except only when high acceleration stress fields are simulated. It has been shown in microgravity studies (4) that as the astronauts were subjected to more environmental stress (during the zero gravity situation), they made substantially greater estimates of the shortest time tasks than what normally occurs in 1 Gz environments. This has been referred to as "The Time Compression Syndrome" (2). In an operationally relevant situation, this corresponds to a pilot having to make a decision on a rapidly moving target which is highly akin to performance tasks emulating the combat situation. Any biased errors here would

result in a critically important compromise of performance.

There are two objective methods (8) to conduct time estimation experiments. The first method is called production (the subject has to produce an interval of time based on his internal clock). We call this first method the "counting" method. The second method (noncounting) is a form of reproduction (the subject has to reproduce a given interval of time based on a visual, auditory, or some other type of a stimulus). A stimulus is presented of an unknown time duration and the subject's task is to reproduce this interval of time based on his subjective estimate under the constraint that he is not allowed to count during this period.

There are many methods to develop these production and reproduction type tasks. In the experiment discussed in the sequel, it was desired to include, as part of the time estimation test, an operationally relevant task (reproduction type) previously tested in microgravity (4), noise chambers (5,6), and under various other experimental conditions (7). It was also of interest to compare the production method versus the reproduction method to better understand the validity of such a test.

Under acceleration stress, many studies have been conducted to better understand changes in human performance but resulting in somewhat mixed results. For example, Brown and Burke (9) showed little change in simple reaction time to a stimulus under levels of 4.6 G stress when the stimulus was detected either in the fovea or in the periphery of the eye. Conversely, Canfield et al. (10) showed reaction time increased with increasing levels of G stress. Especially beyond 5 Gz, the performance was significantly impaired. An interesting study (11) involving three different seat back angles used a choice reaction time task as a performance test. Performance was not affected for acceleration levels less than 6 G for any seat. Above 6 G, however, a 127 degree and 52 degree seat back angle experimental condition resulted in performance degradation but the 67 degree seat back angle had no performance degradation until a level of 7.4 G was achieved. Thus increasing the seat back angle reduces the Gz component and interferes less with the performance task.

In studies of time perception, Underwood (12) lists the two objective methods discussed above as well as third method, which is considered somewhat subjective, termed, "Verbal Estimation". In considering the production type versus the reproduction type, Clausen (13) showed the reproduction method as the most accurate, however, there are some conflicting results in the literature, cf. Carlson and Feinberg (14). The perception of time duration may be influenced by a host of variables. For example, time perception may be altered by what type of reproduction task is chosen (15), the sex of the subject and their method of responding (16), body temperature (17,18), and the time of the day the test is conducted (19). Other variables that have an influence on the perception of time duration includes whether the subjects are bored or busy (20), if an electric shock is used as a penalty for over-estimation (21), modality of the stimulus (sound or vision) (22), or possibly the age of the subject (children versus college students) (23). Thus many variables have to be carefully controlled to delineate time perception changes due only to the acceleration stress.

Methods and Materials:

Equipment: This experiment was conducted on the Dynamic Environment Simulator (DES), a 19 foot radius three-axis centrifuge at Wright-Patterson Air Force Base, Ohio. This centrifuge was programmed to follow the G profile as indicated in figure (1). The DES cab was configured with an aircraft seat at a 30 degree seat back angle, side arm controller, and a 17" CRT mounted directly in front of the subject at a viewing distance of 36". Subjects wore the standard CSU-13 B/P anti-G suit which was inflated with the Alar High-Flow valve. The instrumentation used included measurement of EKG via chest electrodes. The subjects used straining maneuvers, and were equipped with a light bar to indicate levels of graying out prior to possible loss of consciousness.

Subjects: Eight active duty USAF personnel served as subjects. They were all experienced members of the centrifuge panel, 7 males, 1 female and ranged in age from 24 years to 36 years. Physical requirements for the centrifuge panel consist of the standard medical evaluation for enlistment commissioning, EKG, PFT, stress EKG, and a comprehensive series of x-rays (chest, skull and cervical, thoracic and lumbar spine). Due to the nature of the protocol, there were no additional screening tests necessary. Eight subjects finished the experiment while two others were unable to complete the experiment due to their inability to withstand the G stress or because of scheduling conflicts.

Time Estimation Techniques: A production and a reproduction time estimation task were used in this experiment. The production task was

simply the counting of a number of seconds (either 2, 8, or 16 seconds). The video monitor would indicate the numerical value of the time interval for three seconds and then an asterisk would appear as a stimulus indicator. The subject would then count the number of seconds until he felt that the correct time had passed. He then pressed a switch to indicate his/her response.

The second time estimation task involved a noncounting procedure. This task had been used in previous studies (4,5,6,7) and it required the subject to observe on the video display a target going from left to right across the screen for a short period of time. The target disappeared for an invisible portion on the screen and then the subject had to estimate how long a time period would be required for the target to continue moving at that velocity to reach a marker near the right edge of the CRT. Figure (2) illustrates the second time estimation task.

Experimental Design: Each subject participated in five days of testing. The first day was for training and was conducted in the DES cab at 1 Gz. The remaining four data days involved 2 exposures per day to the G profile displayed in figure (1) with a five minute rest between a series A or series B exposure. The order of presentation of the G stress of series A or B were randomized as well as the presentation of the tasks. During the sustained level of G stress, each subject received a set of the 3 tasks (of 2, 8, and 16 seconds), and also during pre and post runs (1 Gz). Within any set, the tasks were randomized with each other. If the counting task was presented during series A, then during the series B exposure, the noncounting task was presented and vice versa. Since each subject had four data day exposures, two days started with a series A exposure, thus the experiment was balanced with respect to both the stress and the performance tasks.

During the first day (in the static 1 Gz condition) of training, the subjects were given feedback on their responses for both the counting and noncounting tasks as to what extent they over or underestimated the time duration. During the subsequent data runs, however, no feedback was given as to the accuracy of the responses. This procedure was also used in the space shuttle experiment (4) and it was chosen to be this way to emulate real world situations. On the first day of training the subjects received the same number of performance tasks as they received on the stress days (days 2-5).

Analysis: Data were first analyzed across all eight subjects. Figure (3) illustrates the noncounting (Jerison task) versus the counting task for the 3 G levels selected in this experiment and the 3 tasks chosen. The shape of the data curve for the noncounting (Jerison) task has the familiar left to right slope downward which has been demonstrated in previous research

(4,5,6,7). The mean ratio (the dependent variable) in this diagram refers to a ratio normalized to the task duration. Therefore, a value of 1.3 for the first task indicates a 30% overestimate of a 2 second task which is equivalent to a total time of 2.6 seconds to estimate this task. Thus, one can compare a task of 2 seconds duration to one at 8 seconds to one at 16 seconds. The asterisks indicate that this point is significantly different from 1.0 (the perfect estimate of this task duration). The counting task in figure (3) is most interesting because it is shown that the only effect occurs at the 5 Gz stress condition for the shortest task which is significantly different from the 1.0 ratio ($p=.0175$) and also significantly different from the experimental conditions of both 1 Gz ($p=.0096$) and 3 Gz ($p=.0123$). The other tasks (8 seconds and 16 seconds), however, were neither significantly different from the ratio 1.0 nor different from each other (within a task, across stress levels). Thus the counting method was the most accurate method as compared to the noncounting (except at 5 Gz for the 2 second task). It is noted that in figure 3, the 5 Gz stress tends to lower the 2 second task estimate for both the counting and noncounting task. Physically this means subjects tend to estimate this task using shorter and shorter time durations.

Across subjects, fatigue effects are very interesting. Looking at these data from the first plateau to the second plateau, one would expect more fatigue on the second plateau. For the counting task, a significant increase ($p=.0019$) of the estimate of the time duration was observed using the 5 Gz runs when averaged across both subjects and the three tasks. This same analysis was repeated at 1 Gz and 3 Gz. The results were increases in the mean estimates of time duration at both 1 Gz and 3 Gz but these results were not significant ($p=.1712$). Thus, the threshold effect seemed to occur at 5 Gz for: (1) Short tasks (counting). (2) Rotation of the noncounting curve (counterclockwise). (3) Fatigue for the second plateau across subjects and tasks as compared to the first plateau of the same days run. Note conditions (1), (2), and (3) did not occur for 1 Gz or 3 Gz. Finally, one subject provided some very interesting data on a day where he was mentally stressed versus a day when he was not preoccupied with mental stress.

Analysis- Within A Subject: One subject provided data of great interest here which needs to be discussed. It is noted that the 5 Gz stress is just on the verge of producing a performance decrement. Perhaps, with some additional mental stress, it may make a difference. The subject reported here was stressed because he normally was a highly motivated subject, however on one day he had problems both with his family and job situation. He related these mental stresses to the physician.

He is an Air Force officer, and had one day's run in a low mental stress condition which was compared to a second day's run when he was in this highly stressed mental condition.

Figures 4a,b,c illustrate the high stress curve (solid line) and the low stress day (dashed line). Going from 4a-c, is in the direction of increasing Gz stress. Each point on the curve is the mean of two data points (except the 1 Gz curve is the average of 6 points). The following results can be seen in figures 4a-c.

- (1) The noncounting task is rotated counter clockwise as stress increases and even more so as the mental stress increases.
- (2) The counting task is amazingly robust to both increases in G stress and increases in mental stress. Note the dashed lines in figures 4a-c provide the baseline; the solid line shifts relative to this line.
- (3) This subject reaches a threshold at 5 Gz with the stress condition as noted in figure 4c. Note the counting values are not affected by the 5 Gz stress because it is barely stressful enough to affect performance. With high mental stress, however, significant performance effects occur as demonstrated in figure 4c.
- (4) Comparing figure 4a to figure 4c for the noncounting (2 second) task, it is seen that the estimate ratio goes from 170% at 1 Gz to 82% at 5 Gz. This is a substantial change in error for such a task.

Finally, from an operationally relevant point of view, the percentage plots illustrated in figures 3, 4a-c somewhat mask the true error. Table I illustrates these mean values in real time. Thus if a subject is 40% off a 2 second task, this is not as operationally relevant as being 10% off on a 16 second task.

Table I - Real Time Values (means across subjects in seconds)

Task Duration	2 sec	8 sec	16 sec
Noncounting			
1 Gz	2.6	8.56	14.72
3Gz	2.6	8.4	14.08
5Gz	2.4	8.96	13.76
overall mean	2.54	8.64	14.24
Counting			
1 Gz	1.84	7.68	15.36
3 Gz	1.86	7.68	15.52
5 Gz	1.68	7.68	15.68
overall mean	1.78	7.68	15.52

Discussion and Conclusions: Data were analyzed across subjects and within a subject. 5 Gz is at the point of compromising performance across subjects in terms of counting short tasks and fatigue. Within a subject the combination of 5 Gz and mental stress can significantly effect the noncounting task. The results of this study indicate that the effect of a subject's ability to estimate the passage of time depends on

several factors. Certain types of tasks seem to be the most affected (short duration counting tasks). Increasing the level of G stress had an effect on the perception of time, but also the amount of mental stress seemed to further compound the errors in the perception of time. In an operationally relevant situation the pilot should be aware of situational awareness (attention anomalies) that may occur at levels above 5 Gz. The pilot may misjudge rapidly moving targets by assuming the targets are going to arrive at a quicker time. By developing counting strategies (except at quick targets), the pilot can improve his ability to estimate time duration.

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Series A = 1-3-5-3-5-1 Gz
 Series B = 1-5-3-5-3-1 Gz

Figure (1) - A Typical Test Day Profile (Series A)

Response Indicator on Stick

Figure (2) - The Non-Counting Task

Figure 3

MEAN RATIO (RESPONSE/TIME)

* = SIGNIFICANTLY DIFFERENT FROM 1.0

Figure 4a (1 GZ)

Figure 4b (3 GZ)

Figure 4c (5 GZ)

